

AN ANALYSIS OF GRAMMATICAL ERRORS ON INSTAGRAM CAPTIONS WRITTEN BY K-POPERS

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to analyze the types of grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers. The existence of social media has become a common communication among K-Popers national and international boundaries. Instagram is one of the social media platforms which has received a lot of attention from K-Popers. K-Popers usually upload their idols' photos or videos on Instagram, and they usually use English as their caption to make it is easy to understand by K-Popers around the world. Through the English captions on Instagram, grammatical errors often occur in their English. This research used descriptive qualitative method. The researcher chose the accounts from hashtag #kpopshoutout. The researcher had figured out the data which were posted on January to April 2021 from six K-Popers which have been chosen in the form of sentences on Instagram captions. Five K-Popers in different accounts which have been chosen by the researcher, they were: @jsoo.yaaa_, @do.exokyung, @bts.bighitofficial, @bts.bighitotfical, and @nutshell.skz. The researcher analyzed 50 captions from six K-Popers accounts. Based on the analysis result by using Dulay's theory, there are four types of grammatical errors based on Surface Strategy Taxonomy, they are omission, addition, mis-formation, and mis-ordering. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that omission was the most type of grammatical error and addition was the least type of grammatical errors that the researcher found in this research.

1. Introduction

Korean Pop or usually called K-Pop is a type of popular music from South Korea. Sue Jin, Lee (2011, p. 86) Korean Wave is a South Korean pop culture that is developed rapidly in various countries in this world so that it develops into a global phenomenon. The fans of Korean Wave have their own uniqueness that creates them different from the fans of other cultures. One of the examples is imitating the looks of an idol group they like. Fandom has its own identity named EXO-L as EXO's fans, ARMY as BTS's fans, NCTzen as NCT's fans, BLINK as Black Pink's fans, REVELUV as Red Velvet's fans, and so on. The existence of social media supports the activities of Korean culture fans. Social media has become a common communication between K-Popers national and international boundaries.

Manning, J (2014, p. 1158) stated that social media is a kind of large range of internet-based and mobile services which make the users can be involved in the online exchange, give a contribution to user-created content, and gather in online communities. The high number and easy access to social media bring the latest news from South Korea to the corners of the world instantly. Korean Wave fandoms usually have their account on social media platforms such as Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, etc. One of the popular social media platforms which are mostly used by people around the globe especially K-Popers in today's digital era is Instagram.

Instagram is a mobile application platform for 2 sharing photos, videos, and stories. Instagram has been downloaded by more than 107 million people around the globe (Instagram, 2021). Instagram has received a lot of attention from K-Popers among the other social media. Through Instagram, they can see what their idols do because Instagram has some features such as Instagram Live, Instagram Stories, IGTV, etc. Many Korean artists nowadays are using Instagram as their social media.

K-Popers usually upload their idols' photos or videos on Instagram, and they usually use English as their caption to make it is easy to understand by K-Popers around the world so they are able to see or give some comments on it because English is an international language which is used by people around this world. Therefore, English is much needed because it plays an important role in communication among K-Pop communities.

Nowadays, English on Instagram captions has become a language teaching and learning tool because it helps the learners either directly or indirectly to develop and improve their skills in writing skills especially in writing descriptive text (Soviyah & Etikaningsih, 2018). Through the English captions on Instagram, grammatical errors often occur in their English.

Grammar is very important both spoken and written language. Every language has their own grammar. It is an essential part of language's use. It can be concluded that is having a good grammar, it will be easier for people to share their ideas, feelings, and messages in a good and right sentence both spoken and written language. There are some aspects of grammar, such as pronouns, tenses, 3 punctuation, subject verb agreement, and so on. However, when learning English, the learners often encounter with grammar and make an error in speaking or writing. Errors and mistakes are something different, these are not the same thing, but most people still misunderstand about both definitions.

According to Corder in Hsu (2013) stated that errors are something which occur repeatedly, it cannot be self-corrected. It can be said that errors are systematic. Mistakes are something which can be self-corrected, so it is not systematic. During learning a language, it cannot be separated from making errors. Making errors are seen positively because from making errors, the learners can learn something, it can be considered as a way to improve their skills and it can be considered as a way of building the flexibility of the learners. K-Popers who use English Instagram captions cannot be separated from making errors, especially K-Popers who use English as Foreign Language because English is not the official language of their country.

Based on this phenomenon, the researcher analyzed grammatical errors which arise on English captions written in K-Poper Instagram accounts. This study aimed to determine the types of grammatical errors that often occur in the activities and interaction among K-Popers' in posting their photos or videos on Instagram using English caption.

The researcher collected the data by taking screenshots on the posts which are contain of grammatical errors. Then, the researcher analyzed the data based on the types of grammatical errors to answer the research and the results of this research can be used as learning by readers so as not to make the same errors when writing captions on Instagram.

2. Literature Review

2.1 K-Pop

The Korean wave or Hallyu in Korean language, refers to the significantly increased popularity of South Korean culture around the world. Hallyu is a reference to the success of South Korean cultural phenomena which attract international attention. Hallyu also known as Korean Wave is defined as a south Korean cultural wave phenomenon consists of several cultural contents. The contents are movies, K-Drama, K-Pop, K-Fashion, and so on. Hallyu is a designation given by journalists in China when seeing news about K-Drama and K-Pop dominate the mail news and magazines in China in 1998. Seok Lee in Sari and Jamaan (2019), Beijing Youth Daily is one of the China first used the term Hallyu in its report on the success of the K-Pop idol group is holding its concert in Beijing in 2011 November 1999. Since then, the term Hallyu has often been used to describe the popularity of South Korean culture abroad. The South Korean culture contents are K-Drama, K-Pop, K-Fashion, and so on. K-Pop is currently synonymous with idol groups (boybands and girl bands) and solo singer which become an icon or face of Hallyu itself. While K-Pop with its idol groups is quite different, especially from Western music, it is easy to see why many people have become addicted to it now. The melodies are catchy, the choreographies are impressive and the group members are beautiful to the eye. There is usually a lot of effort into making the music videos look cool and high quality, even when it is just the group members dancing. The groups have specific styles to help them stand out.

2.2 K-Poper

K-Poper is a term for Korean Pop fans. The majority of today's K-Popers are teenagers. This is because adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, a period of seeking identity, a period where they feel challenged to prove their intellectual abilities. Adolescents generally identify in a character who is considered an idol, by imitating the behavior, habits, and what the idol is wearing. In general, teenagers idolize someone who

are charming, smart, and kind. Moreover, K-Pop music is suitable for adolescents and the idols who perform it are still in the teenage to adult age range.

Mustikawati (2020, p. 369-370) K-Popers not only consume a range of Korean Wave entertainment contents, but also they actively participate in Korean culture, such as food, language, and traditional events. Some K-Popers show aggressive collective activities for their chosen K-Pop stars on social media across national boundaries. Not only promote their specific subjects, but also the fandoms consume them by recreating the original subject with high levels of attachment. Popular culture fans express their desires, values, and identity by consuming the subject, and they sometimes follow whatever their chosen stars do.

As a part of global cultural content, K-Pop has been building relations by bridging global and local K-Popers. K-Pop fandoms have been establishing a transnational cultural community through the internet, social media, and mobile technology. Online community may be a social place for people who share common interest and issues with online users and actively interact with one another, the sensation of solidarity among the people can be developed. K-Popers delivered the Korean Wave contents through Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, and online fan pages so as to share the contents with and to make cultural ties with the K-Popers in local and global areas.

2.3 Instagram

Instagram is one of the famous social media platforms in today's era. Instagram is a mobile application platform for sharing photos, videos, and stories, it offers some features which permits its users to build up interaction with the other users. Instagram was found by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger in October, 2010. From official Instagram website, Instagram has been downloaded by more than 107 million people around the globe (Instagram, 2021). Instagram allows its users to edit and upload photos and videos through a mobile application. Instagram provides some features which are interesting, such as photo filters, direct message, group messaging, picture editing, location tagging, Instagram story, live video streaming, IGTV, and reels. Instagram users make connections with the other Instagram users by following each other's profiles which allows them to see the content posted on those profiles and give responses or reactions in the form of likes or comments. When a user follows another user, they can see all postings and it can be shown in the news feed. In posting photo or video on Instagram, people usually use a caption. A caption, also known as a cut line. It is the text which appears below the image to give description or information which is related to the picture or video which is uploaded. Most captions point up to something in the image which is not obvious, such as its relevance to the text. According to Grayam (2010), a caption is a brief description, definition, explanation, information, or detail accompanying an illustration, the part of a legal document which gives the important details of a photograph. In the other hand, a caption is usually related to the pictures, because it gives a brief description and detail information of the picture.

2.4 Grammatical Errors

2.4.1. The definition of grammatical error

Grammar is an essential part of language's use both spoken and written language, it is an important element of a language. According to Richard and Schmidt (2010, p. 251-252),

grammar is a depiction of the construction of a language and how language units, for example, words and expressions are shaped into sentences. A grammatical error is an error in grammar. It can be said that grammatical error is a term utilized in prescriptive grammar to explain an instance of faulty, unconventional, or controversial usage. Grammatical errors often occur both spoken and written language. Among the four skills such as listening, reading, writing, and speaking, writing is the most complicated skills which have to be mastered because it needs deep knowledge and deep thinking to produce words, sentences, and paragraphs (Kumala, et al, 2018). To produce meaningful sentences, the writer must have good ideas, grammar competence, and language skills. Therefore, grammar is the most important elements in producing the sentences (Kharmilah and Narius, 2019). On the other hand, grammar and writing have relation and connect each other.

2.4.2. The distinction between error and mistake

There is a distinction between error and mistake. Error and mistake are not the same thing, but most people still most understand about both definitions. Corder in Sattayatham (2013) errors are systematic in nature being, "errors of competence" and mistakes are, "errors of performance" which are not systematic. It can be said that errors cannot be self-corrected. Mistake is accident. We know it is wrong, but the wrong word slips out. A learner often makes mistakes in writing or speaking because they lack of fatigue, attention, careless, and the other aspects of performance. Mistakes can be self-corrected when attention is called because mistakes are not systematic. On the other hand, an error is systematic because it occurs repeatedly, so, it is not recognized as an error. Errors are classified according to pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar, production of wrong communication effect, and misunderstanding of a speaker's intention or meaning. In speaking, error is more formal than mistake. In technical context, error can be interpreted more broadly and has no such connotation, while a mistake happens because of decision, human action, and judgement.

2.4.3 Types of Grammatical Errors

According to Dulay, Burt, and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32), classified the types of errors based on Surface Strategy Taxonomy, they are:

a. Omission

Dulay, Burt, and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32) omission or deletion means the absence of some item which is must appear in the sentence. It usually happens in the first stages in second language acquisition. It can be said that omission is the type of error which is characterized by the absence of an item which must appear in a well-formed utterance. Morphemes or words can be famed into two classes, they are content words and grammatical words. Content morphemes is carried the most common of the referential meaning of a sentence, these are nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, etc. Grammatical words include noun and verb inflection (-s, es, ed, ing), the article (a, an, the), verb auxiliaries (am, is, are, will, can, may, etc.), and preposition (in, on, at, etc.). For example: *She is good student*. There is the omission of the article "a", it should be "*She is a good student*"

b. Addition

Addition is the opposite of omission. Dulay, Burt, and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32), addition errors are characterized by the presence of an item which must not appear in a well-formed language. There are three types of addition errors, they are:

1) Double markings

It is caused by the failure to delete certain items that are required in some linguistic constructions. For example: *She does not eats*. There is double marking which should be "*She does not eat*". In the most English sentences, some semantic features such as tense may be marked only once.

2) Regularization

It is a type of errors in which a marker that is typically added to a linguistic item is erroneously added to exceptional items of the given class that do not take a marker. For example: *sheeps* instead of *sheep*.

3) Simple addition

It is the use of an item which should not appear in well-formed utterance. Simple addition errors characterize all addition errors. For example: *The fishes doesn't live in the water*. There is a simple addition which should be "The *fish* doesn't live in the water"

c. Mis-formation

Dulay, Burt, and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32), mis-formation errors are characterized by the use of the wrong form of structure, it happened when the learner supplies something although it is incorrect. There are three types of mis-formation errors, they are:

1) Regularization

Regularization errors fall under the mis-formation category are those in which a regular marker is used in place of an irregular one. For example: *He rided his motorcycle*. There is a regularization errors, there is a wrong change of verb "ride", it should be "*He rode his motorcycle*".

2) Archi-forms

Archi-forms errors are the selection of one number of a class of forms to represent others in the class is common characteristic of all stages of second language acquisition. For example: *This pencils are mine*. There is an archi-forms errors, this is not appropriate to plural. It should be "*These pencils are mine*".

3) Alternating forms

This error is indicated by an error in selection or use the right form of the word. It caused by the learners' grammar and vocabulary development. For example: *I seen you yesterday*. The sentence above has the wrong verb because it indicates past tense. The alternating forms should be "*I saw you yesterday*".

d. Mis-ordering

Dulay, Burt and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32) mis-ordering errors are characterized by the incorrect placement of a morpheme or group of morphemes in an utterance. In other words, mis-ordering errors are occurred when the learner used a grammatical morpheme or group of morphemes in a wrong place of sentence formulation. Mis-ordering errors occur systematically for both first language and second language learners in constructions which have been acquired. For example: 1. *You do not understand what is my question.*

2. *What you are thinking about?*

The mis-ordering of the two sentences above lies in the word "is" and "are". It should be:

1. *You do not understand what my question is.*

2. *What are you thinking about?*

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

As stated in problem of the research, this research aimed to analyze the types of grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers. Thus, in this research, the researcher used descriptive research as the method in conducting the data. Descriptive research is designed to obtain information concerning the current status phenomena. In qualitative research, there is a little or no statistic. In the other words, qualitative generally uses words rather than numbers or concepts which can be identified, and rich description of phenomena which can be produced. The results of this research are not written in the form of tables and figures with statistical measures, but it is illustrated in the form of describing words for the results.

3.2 Research Location

The location in this research was on social media platform. Social media platform where the researcher uses to conduct the research was Instagram. The researcher used his personal Instagram account to find out the data. The researcher collected the data by looking for the captions which contain of grammatical errors in K-Popers' accounts which have been chosen with hashtag #kpopshoutout which were posted from January to April 2021.

3.3 Research Subject

A research subject is a person who becomes the object of the research which is being investigated. The subjects of this research were five K-Popers' Instagram accounts or 50 Instagram posts with hashtag #kpopshoutout and how are the types grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers.

3.4 Research Instruments

According to Sugiyono (2013, p. 223), in qualitative research, the researchers as human instruments serve to find out the focus research, selecting informants as data sources, collecting data, assess data quality, analyze data, interpret data, and build the conclusion to his findings. Hence, deep qualitative research "the researcher is the key instrument." Be a

researcher is a key instrument in qualitative research. Therefore, in qualitative research, the instrument is the researcher themselves. Hence, the researcher should be legalized or validated by themselves in conducting the research. The researcher collected the data from English captions written by K-Popers which have been chosen who use English as their captions with hashtag #kpopshoutout which posted on January to April 2021, then the researcher directly took source from the English captions which contain of grammatical errors written by K-Popers. The researcher analyzed the captions based on the types of grammatical errors.

3.5 Data and Data Source

In this research, the data were in the form of descriptive qualitative data and the researcher uses qualitative data procedure for the data analysis. The researcher analyzed the types of grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers. The data sources were 50 posts along with the captions which taken from 5 K-Popers accounts with hashtag #kpopshoutout. The researcher used his personal Instagram account to find out the data and to look for Instagram captions from K-Popers which contain of grammatical errors. The researcher chose K-Popers Instagram accounts who use English as their captions in hashtag #kpopshoutout

3.6 Data Collection Technique

Collecting the data can be done in any settings, any sources, and any ways. There are five data collecting techniques, they are: observation, interview, questionnaire, documentation and triangulation. In this research, the researcher used documentation in collecting the data by taking screenshots to get information and result of the research. Screenshot provides striking descriptive data which is often used for subjective understanding and is a product which is often analyzed inductive. In collecting the data, the researcher focused on the aim of this research which is to find out how are the types of grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers

3.7 Data Analysis

According to Sugiyono (2013, p. 245), there are three steps to analyze the data in descriptive qualitative study, they are: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing or verification. The first step was data reduction. It means the strategy of selecting, identifying, classifying and coding the data which are well-thought-of important. In conducting research, the researcher will get much data. Therefore, the researcher must select the data which can give valuable information in the research. Reducing the information in this research, the researcher is chosen by analyze the types of grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers. In this step, the researcher collected the data by observing the captions which contain of grammatical errors in 5 K-Popers' Instagram accounts which have been chosen.

The second step was data display. It refers to show the data which have been reduced in the form of sentence, narrative, or table in order to help the researcher in understanding the data. In this step, the researcher classified the English captions based on their types, whether belongs to omission, addition, mis-formation, and mis-ordering. In displaying data, the researcher analyzed from data reduction then described the data which have been reduced into sentence form or narrative form in order to be easier to understand. For the last step was

drawing conclusion or verification. It was the final step to answer the problem statement which is to find out the types of grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers. In this research, the researcher drew conclusion or verified the data by rechecking from data reduction and data display. Therefore, the researcher can draw conclusion after rechecking from the data reduction and data display.

4. Findings

4.1. The Types of Grammatical Errors on Instagram Captions Written by K-Popers

Table 1. The Types of Grammatical Errors on Instagram Captions Written by K-Popers

No.	Accounts' Name	Types of Grammatical Errors				Total Errors of Each Account
		Omission	Addition	Mis-formation	Mis-ordering	
1.	@jsoo.yaaa_	10				10
2	@do.exokyung	4		5	1	10
3.	@bts.bighotofficial	9			1	10
4.	@bts.bighitotfical	1		8	1	10
5	@nutshell.skz	6	2	2		10
The Total of Grammatical Errors		30	2	15	3	50

Figure 1. The types of grammatical errors written by K-Popers

5. Discussion

From the data above, it can be seen that the type of grammatical errors that K-Popers made the most are omission errors. Omission errors are the first rank of types of grammatical errors that the researcher found in this research. Dulay, Burt, and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32), omission errors are omitting or deleting of an item which must appear in well-formed utterance. It can be said that omission errors are happened when the learners or speakers omit the grammatical morphemes which must appear or must be used in well-formed utterance. There were 30 captions in this research which contain of omission errors. All the K-Popers accounts have their errors in omission. On Instagram accounts of *@jsoo.yaaa_* there were 10 captions which contain of omission errors. The researcher found that this account has the weaknesses in omission because most all of the captions from this account's posts were containing of omission errors. On Instagram account of *@do.exokyung*, there were 4 captions which contain of omission error that the researcher found in this research. On Instagram account of *@bts.bighitofficial*, there were 9 captions which contain of omission error. It can be said that this account has the weaknesses in omission like *@jsoo.yaaa_* do. On Instagram account of *@bts.bighitofficial* there was 1 caption which contain of omission error. On Instagram account of *@nutshell.skz*, there were 6 captions which contain of omission errors.

Based on the previous research from Faiza, et al (2020), omission error was the first rank of errors with the total number 39 participants with the rate of 78%. Language learners omitted grammatical morphemes much more frequently than content words of second language acquisition. Omission errors happen because the learners or speakers were still lack of form or grammar that is supposed to have in the sentence but the learners omit it or delete it. After analyzing the data, the researcher found out that omission of grammatical morpheme especially in verb inflection was the most errors that K-Popers made in this research.

The second rank of the types of grammatical errors that the researcher found in this research was mis-formation. Dulay, et al in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32), mis-formation errors are characterized by the using of the wrong form or structure. There are three types of mis-formation errors, they are regularization, archi-forms, and alternating forms. Mis-formation errors in alternating forms were the most type of mis-formation errors that the researcher found in this research. Alternating forms is indicated by the error in selecting the right form of the word and it is caused by the learners' grammar and vocabulary development. On Instagram accounts of *@do.exokyung*, there were 5 captions which contain of mis-formation errors especially in alternating forms. On Instagram account of *@bts.bighitofficial*, there were 8 captions which contain of mis-formation errors. It can be said that this account has the weakness in mis-formation error especially in alternating forms and regularization. On Instagram account *@nutshell.skz*, there were only 2 captions which contain of mis-formation errors especially in alternating forms. From 15 data which contain of mis-formation error, it can be concluded that from five K-Popers accounts which have been chosen, mostly accounts have weaknesses in mis-formation errors especially in alternating forms.

The third rank of the types of grammatical errors that the researcher found in this research was mis-ordering errors. Dulay, Burt, and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011, p. 32),

mis-ordering errors are the incorrect placement of a morpheme or group in an utterance. It occurs systematically for both L1 and L2 learners specifically direct and indirect questions. The researcher found mis-ordering errors only one caption on each Instagram account of *@do.exokyung*, *@bts.bighotofficial*, and *@bts.bighitotfical*.

The last rank of the types of grammatical errors that the researcher found in this research was addition errors. Dulay, Burt, and Krashen in Puspasari and Romadon (2011. p. 32), addition errors are adding an item which must not appear in well-formed utterance. It can be said that addition errors are the opposite of omissions. There are three types of addition errors, they are double markings, regularization, and simple addition. The researcher found this type of grammatical errors only on Instagram account of *@nutshell.skz*. There were only 2 captions which contain of addition error, especially in simple addition. Based on the previous research from Puspasari and Romadon (2011), addition error was the third rank of the types of grammatical errors that they found in their research. Although, addition error was the last rank of the types of grammatical errors that the researcher found in this research.

From the data in this research, the researcher found that one caption not only contain of one type of grammatical errors, it can be more than one type. Each Instagram account have their own weaknesses. For example, on Instagram accounts *@jsoo.yaaa_* and *@bts.bighotofficial* have their weaknesses in omission errors and *@bts.bighitotfical* has weakness in mis-formation errors. The researcher found a lot of the posts along with the captions which contain of grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers. While doing this research, the researcher examined the topic and analyzed about the types of grammatical errors based on Dulay's theory. The researcher used his personal Instagram accounts to find out the data and looked for the English captions which contain of grammatical errors from five K-Popers accounts which have been chosen. Those posts and captions were not always consisting of the types of grammatical errors based on Dulay's theory. There were other types of grammatical errors that the researcher found when the researcher analyzed the data. Those errors were misspelling, capitalization, and punctuation. When analyzing the data, the researcher did not mention the types of grammatical errors which were not listed by Dulay. However, the researcher simply justified what the other types of grammatical errors such as misspelling, capitalization, and punctuation should be, without mentioning and explaining those types when the researcher analyzed the data. Based on the problem of this research which was to find out how are grammatical errors on Instagram captions written by K-Popers, from the 50 data which have been collected by the researcher from five K-Popers Instagram accounts, it can be concluded that omission is the highest or the most common grammatical errors and addition is the lowest or the least grammatical errors that the researcher found in this research.

6. Conclusion

The researcher had figured out the data which were posted on January to April 2021 from five K-Popers which have been chosen in the form of sentences on Instagram captions. Five K-Popers in different accounts which have been chosen by the researcher, they were: *@jsoo.yaaa_*, *@do.exokyung*, *@bts.bighotofficial*, *@bts.bighitotfical*, and *@nutshell.skz*. Based on the analysis result by using Dulay's theory, it can be concluded that omission was

the most type of grammatical error that the researcher found in this research, especially on Instagram accounts of @jsoo.yaaa_ and @bts.bighotofficial . In this research, addition was the least types of grammatical errors that the researcher found. The researcher found this type of errors only on Instagram account of @nutshell.skz with the total number of errors 2 of 50. K-Popers mostly use English captions just for their enjoyment. Moreover, they use English captions for fanboying or fangirling to express their hobbies. Therefore, they do not notice the grammatical errors when they write Instagram captions. There can be some reasons why K-Popers have grammatical errors, such as they are using English as foreign language or English as second language in their daily life, so they do not notice or do not care about grammatical errors. The important point for them is the others understand what they mean on Instagram captions because the use of caption itself is to give brief description, explanation, information, and detail of the pictures.

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